

The Guideline of Wellness Tourism Development: A Case Study of Natural Hot Spring and Hot Spring Tour Route, Chiangmai Province

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Abstract

The eight potential natural hot spring attractions in Chiang Mai are ThepPhanom hot springs, San Kamphaeng hot springs, Doi Saket hot spring, Bang Pong Ang hot springs, Ban Mai Nong Bua hot springs, Fang hot springs, NongKhrok hot springs and Pong Dueat hot springs. Nevertheless, although each hot spring has the potential for being a recreational facility, some are found to be recreational only. Moreover, the resources usage cannot meet the needs of tourists. It can be seen from the congestion of tourists during the holidays and weekend period. A lack of knowledge in the management, the equipment and facilities maintenance in the area have been causing of the problem. Moreover, a lack of measures to study the social impact of tourism both now and in the future. The objective in this study were to study and analyse data on the potential natural hot spring sources and the suitability of the developing into a new spa city tourist destination and a hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai. The study was adopted the qualitative method by using the in-depth interview for evaluating the satisfaction to obtain the main standard issues and the assessment of the potential. In the in-depth interviews process was used 15 key informants consisted of 4 expertise comprising 1) The Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports 2) The Vice Chairman of the Tourism Council of Thailand 3) The Director of the Department of Personnel Standards Development of the Tourism 4) The Specialists in Tourism Development from the Department of Tourism. Moreover, the local management and representatives of the government agencies in the area all total 4 people. The academics in health tourism all total three persons. The private sector from tourism industry two persons and the community who are serving hot springs business two persons. Next, the focus group discussion aimed to verify the strategies for the developing the natural hot spring resources to a spa town, and the hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai with 30 key informants. The investigators found that, the potential of the hot spring tourism route of Chiang Mai province by using 6 potential factors to analyze, it was found that the hot spring tourism route of Chiang Mai can be integrated of all 8 tourist attractions in Chiang Mai. Moreover, it is suitable, and there is the potential to accommodate the tourists, whether the accommodation, or the restaurants. Including with, the convenience of transportation and the participation of the community in the management of that attraction which can be said that Chiang Mai is very suitable prepared as a tourist route for hot springs city.

Introduction

The wellness tourism has linking and promoting all tourism sectors, which is one of the ten targeted tourism industries as a means of driving the world's future economy. This is partly due to the current interest in health, promoting quality of life and entering an aging society from the change in the population structure with more elderly people. Moreover, occupational stress, lifestyle stress, failure from conventional medical care causes people have started to focus more on their health in a way to prevent illness. Furthermore, people are more give heed in both physical and mental health including beauty and anti-aging. These travelers are the more affordable, ready to pay more for healthier products and services. Besides, Health tourism as a form of tourism that provides holistic health care with the aim of promoting, healing and rejuvenating the body, mind and spirit (Smith and Kelly, 2006). Furthermore, health tourism is a journey to appreciate the beauty of tourist attractions and relaxation. The participating in health activities help to create balance for the body, mind and spirit as well (Chen et al, 2008).

Nowadays, the new generation of Thai people are increasingly paying attention to their physical and mental health. Many health tourism sites have arisen and have been developed into a more modern system. The survey and development of natural hot springs in Chiang Mai is considered to be promoted as a health tourism destination of the country. The 8 potential natural hot spring attractions of Chiang Mai include ThepPhanom Hot Springs, San Kamphaeng Hot Springs, Doi Saket Hot Spring, Bang Pong Ang hot springs, Ban Mai Nong Bua Hot Springs, Fang Hot Springs, NongKhrok Hot Springs, Pong Hot Springs. Most of them will be used mainly for recreation and tourism and natural therapy. The previous studying the potential of health tourism in natural hot springs in, it was found that basic services and activities found in various hot spring sources such as natural hot spring services, accommodation and room service, organizing excursion activities, recreational services and other facilities such as traditional massage services, food and beverage service, etc. The study of the potential of the 8 hot springs in Chiang Mai, it was found that each of the hot springs had potential in the level of recreation, for example, some of them were just recreational sites. Moreover, some places were still only partially useful, such as, there were create a soaking pond, but there was still not enough quantity to meet the needs of tourists. Furthermore, there were the congestion during holidays and Saturdays and Sundays. Beside, a lack of knowledge and understanding of the management and the maintenance of equipment and facilities in the area, as well as a lack of measures to study the social impact from tourism in the future (NiphonChuamuangphan et al., 2013). Therefore, in order to meet the changing tourism demands, it is necessary to analyze data on potential natural hot springs and the suitability of developing into a new spa city tourist destination and hot spring travel routes. Moreover, the study will be highlighting the connectivity in tourism in the Chiang Mai area. Furthermore, to formulate a strategy for developing natural hot spring resources to spa towns and hot spring travel routes and presenting guidelines for the development of the natural hot springs and hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai.

Research Objectives

The objective of this research was to study and analyze data on potential natural hot spring sources and the suitability of developing into a new spa city tourist destination and hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai, and to formulate a strategy for developing natural hot spring resources to a spa town and the hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai.

Research Methods

This study utilized the qualitative research for studying The Guideline of Wellness Tourism Development: A Case Study of Natural Hot Spring and Hot Spring Tour Route, Chiangmai Province.

Qualitative Study

Participants

The study was adopted the qualitative method by using the in-depth interview for evaluating the satisfaction to obtain the main standard issues and the assessment of the potential. In the in-depth interviews process was used 15 key informants consisted of 4 expertise comprising 1) The Permanent Secretary of the Ministry of Tourism and Sports. 2) The Vice Chairman of the Tourism Council of Thailand. 3) The Director of the Department of Personnel Standards Development of the Tourism. 4) The Specialists in Tourism Development from the Department of Tourism. Moreover, the local management and representatives of the government agencies in the area all total 4 people. The academics in health tourism all total three persons. The private sector from tourism industry two persons and the community who are serving hot springs business two persons. Next, the focus group discussion aimed to verify the strategies for the developing the natural hot spring resources to a spa town, and the hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai with 30 key informants.

Instrument.

The researchers used the semi-structure interview for the in-depth interview and the focus group.

Results

In-depth interview results

The Guideline of Wellness Tourism Development: A Case Study of Natural Hot Spring and Hot Spring Tour Route, Chiangmai Province. The analysis of the data in the in-depth interview was evaluated the potential of natural hot springs and hot spring tourism routes. The evaluating of the satisfaction to obtain the main standard issues and the assessment of the potential were used by descriptive statistics with content analysis with

the 15 key informants. The levels were divided into 5 levels, which are excellent, very good, good, moderate and should be improved.

Table.1. showing the result of evaluating the satisfaction to obtain the main standard issues

Main Standard Issues	Results of Data Analysis		Standard Level
	\bar{X}	S.D.	
1. ThepPhanom hot springs			
Water quality which appropriates for services	4.00	0.00	Very good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	3.60	0.23	Very good
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	4.13	0.00	Very good
Security service management for service users	3.43	0.00	Good
Environmental management	4.60	0.00	Excellent
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.95	0.05	Very good
2. San Kamphaeng hot springs			
Water quality which appropriates for services	4.20	0.00	Very good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	4.00	0.00	Very good
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	4.46	0.07	Very good
Security service management for service users	3.81	0.08	Very good
Environmental management	4.40	0.35	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	4.17	0.10	Very good
3. Doi Saket hot spring			
Water quality which appropriates for services	4.20	0.00	Very good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	3.80	0.00	Very good
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	4.63	0.00	Excellent
Security service management for service users	3.29	0.00	Very good
Environmental management	4.33	0.12	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	4.05	0.02	Very good
4. Bang Pong Ang hot spring			
Water quality which appropriates for services	4.20	0.00	Very good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	3.58	0.04	Good
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	4.14	0.25	Very good
Security service management for service users	4.07	0.12	Very good
Environmental management	3.38	0.08	Good
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.87	0.10	Very good
5. Ban Mai Nong Bua hot spring			
Water quality which appropriates for services	3.07	0.58	Good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	1.96	0.45	Moderate
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	2.96	0.07	Good
Security service management for service users	1.19	0.16	Should be improved
Environmental management	2.47	0.12	Moderate
Summary of the overall assessment results	2.33	0.28	Moderate
6. Fang hot spring			
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	4.49	0.19	Very good
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	4.92	0.07	Excellent

Main Standard Issues	Results of Data Analysis		Standard Level
	\bar{X}	S.D.	
rooms/lockers			
Security service management for service users	4.29	0.25	Very good
Environmental management	4.20	0.40	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	4.47	0.21	Excellent
7. NongKhrok Hot Springs			
Water quality which appropriates for services	3.40	0.00	Good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	1.87	0.00	Moderate
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	1.88	0.00	Moderate
Security service management for service users	1.14	0.00	Should be improved
Environmental management	2.60	0.00	Good
Summary of the overall assessment results	2.19	0.00	Should be improved
8. Pong Dua Hot Springs			
Water quality which appropriates for services	4.27	0.23	Very good
Management of hot spring baths/hot spring baths pool or swimming pool	3.58	0.10	Very good
Management of shower rooms/toilets/changing rooms/lockers	4.63	0.22	Excellent
Security service management for service users	3.86	0.00	Very good
Environmental management	4.13	0.42	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	4.09	0.19	Very good
overall assessment results	3.64	0.12	Very good

Interpretation of table-1.

The results of the analysis of data from the assessment of the evaluation the satisfaction, and to obtain the main standard issues of natural hot spring health tourism sites consisted of 5 aspects consisted of suitable water quality for service, management of hot spring baths, hot spring baths or swimming pool, management of shower rooms, toilets, changing rooms, lockers, security management, environmental management. It was found that the average results obtained from the 5 main standards of ThepPhanom hot springs attractions were of high mainstream standards (\bar{X} =3.95). San Kamphaeng hot springs had moderate mainstream standards (\bar{X} =4.17). Doi Saket hot spring had a high main standard (mean score 4.05). Bang Pong Ang hot spring had a high mainstream standard (\bar{X} = 3.87). Ban Mai Nong Bua hot spring had a low mainstream standard (\bar{X} = 2.33). Fang hot spring had a high main standard. The highest (\bar{X} =4.47). NongKhrok Hot Springs had a low mainstream standard (\bar{X} =2.19) and Pong Dua Hot Springs had a high mainstream hot spring (\bar{X} =4.09).

Table.2. The results of the assessment of the potential of being a health tourism attraction in the natural hot spring type of Chiang Mai Province

Potential issues	Results of Data Analysis		Standard Level
	\bar{X}	S.D.	
1. ThepPhanom hot springs			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	3.29	0.25	Good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	3.60	0.00	Very good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	3.33	0.00	Good
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.41	0.08	Good
2. San Kamphaeng hot springs			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	3.62	0.08	Very good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	4.20	0.00	Very good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	3.67	0.00	Very good

Potential issues	Results of Data Analysis		Standard Level
	\bar{X}	S.D.	
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.83	0.03	Very good
3. Doi Saket hot spring			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	3.67	0.22	Very good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	3.47	0.12	Good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	3.61	0.10	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.58	0.15	Very good
4. Bang Pong Ang hot spring			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	3.07	0.46	Good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	3.39	0.19	Good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	4.38	0.00	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.61	0.22	Very good
5. Ban Mai Nong Bua hot spring			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	2.95	0.33	Good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	2.87	0.12	Good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	2.50	0.00	Moderate
Summary of the overall assessment results	2.77	0.15	Good
6. Fang hot spring			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	4.00	0.00	Very good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	4.13	0.23	Very good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	3.83	0.17	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.99	0.13	Very good
7. NongKhrok Hot Springs			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	2.86	0.00	Good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	2.60	0.00	Good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	2.06	0.10	Moderate
Summary of the overall assessment results	2.51	0.03	Good
8. Pong Dua Hot Springs			
There is a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest.	4.33	0.30	Very good
Has the potential to accommodate tourists	3.60	0.20	Very good
Management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability	3.72	0.54	Very good
Summary of the overall assessment results	3.88	0.35	Very good
An overview of the potential of health tourism destinations	3.45	0.14	Good

Interpretation of table-2.

The results of the assessment of the potential of being a natural hot spring health tourism attraction consisted of 3 aspects which were a natural hot spring health attraction as a point of interest, the potential to accommodate tourists, management of utilization of surrounding areas for sustainability. As for the results of the assessment of the potential of being a natural hot spring tourist attraction in Chiang Mai, it was found that the average result obtained from the potential of all 3 aspects of the hot spring attraction. ThePhanom hot springs had moderate potential (\bar{X} =3.41), San Kamphaeng hot springs had high potential (\bar{X} =3.83,) Doi Saket hot springs had high potential (\bar{X} =3.58,) Ban Pong Ang hot springs had high potential (\bar{X} =3.61), Ban Mai Nong Bua hot springs had moderate potential (\bar{X} =2.77), Fang hot springs had high potential (\bar{X} =3.99), NongKhrok hot springs had moderate potential (\bar{X} =2.51) and Pong Tua hot springs had moderate potential at a high level (\bar{X} =3.88).

(Draft) the strategies formulation development natural hot spring resources to a spa town and the hot spring travel routes in Chiang Mai.

It could be concluded which led to the preparation of strategies formulation to develop the natural hot springs and the hot spring travel routes as follows:

- There was still a lack of connection with tourism in the Chiang Mai area and there were no strategy to develop to be the natural hot spring source into a spa town and a hot spring tourist route.
- Income generation and income distribution to communities and neighboring communities.
- There was still a lack of the connection with the tourism in the Chiang Mai area and there were no strategies to develop a natural hot spring source into a spa town and a hot spring tourist route.
- Development of the services, safety, public transport, cleanliness according to infrastructure factors to meet standards.
- Building a tourism network to create a link to tourist attractions.
- Creating important databases of the tourist attractions, tourists, the organizing knowledge of tourist attractions, the creation of a story for the tourist attraction to inherit and carry on effectively.
- Enhancing activities that attract tourists and remains unique of the local identity.
- Product Creation and creating added value for the community products.
- The development of marketing promotion and public relations.

Focus Group Result

The brainstorming of the opinions from 30 key informants among the public sector, the private sector, the community, and the network partners related to health tourism on the subject of the development of natural hot spring resources from ThepPhanom hot springs, San Kamphaeng hot springs, Doi Saket hot spring, Bang Pong Ang hot springs, Ban Mai Nong Bua hot springs, Fang hot springs, NongKhrok hot springs and Pong Dueat hot springs. The strengthen and the needs to be improved was carried out by dividing the participants into 3 groups by assorted departments under the jurisdiction to obtain the information and the opinion from all sectors which could be concluded as follows:

Table.3. Brainstorming opinions and the suggestions on the conceptual framework for the development of the natural hot spring resources.

Characteristics of Doi Saket Hot Springs	
Strength	Weakness
1.It is a natural hot spring source arising from the plains which is surrounded by rice paddies with beautiful surrounding mountains.	1.Lack of improvements in facilities such as parking lots, restrooms, or buildings such as parking lots, first aid rooms, etc.
2.Transportation routes are convenient for accessing hot springs.	2.The surrounding landscape is still lacking to be naturally beautiful.
3. No entrance fee.	3. The staff still lack English skills to communicate with foreign tourists.
4. Hot spring source There are signs to provide tourists with detailed instructions on various methods and methods.	
5. There are facilities for the disabled.	
6. The area is managed by the community. by employing people in the community as service personnel.	
7. Hot springs have services such as hot springs for bathing and foot baths. Thai massage services are available. Moreover, Community enterprises have products that have passed the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) standards for distribution to tourists.	
8. Water quality is checked by the Faculty of Pharmacy. Chiang Mai University The water will be analysed every 6 months.	
9. A water tank was built to separate the minerals in the hot spring area.	

Conclusion

The results of the study analysed the potential of the hot spring tourism route in Chiang Mai which has been analysed through 6 potential factors, which the 8 hot spring sources are linked to hot spring tourism routes in Chiang Mai. The details of the analysis of 6 potential factors are as follows:

(1) Potential in terms of tourist attractions: All the 8 tourist attractions combine to become a hot spring tourist route in Chiang Mai. Moreover, all the 8 hot springs have the potential to accommodate tourists of the attraction properly. In addition, there are the potential of personnel to serve tourists. Furthermore, there are suitable environment to be a tourist destination, and there are the facilities available to serve tourists.

(2) Accommodation potential: There are enough accommodation for tourists who want to stay overnight, such as Baan Doi Saket homestay and Ban Mae Kampong homestay.

(3) Restaurant potential: Along the 8 tourist routes, there are restaurants nearby with a variety of food.

(4) Transport potential: There is transportation connected to other places. Moreover, the roads are safe for driving.

(5) Potential for participation of the local communities: Community are involved in taking care of tourist attractions by participating in tourism management. Furthermore, the emergence of the entrepreneurs to engage in developing tourist attraction.

(6) There are tourist resources of nearby areas: There are resources and publicity for other attractions in Chiang Mai by making signs to publicize by showing a route linking various tourist attractions of Chiang Mai.

Recommendations

- It is necessary to study and analyse the data from many elements to come up with the guidelines for the developing tourism strategies and the guidelines for the development of the natural hot spring resources towards a spa town along with development guidelines to connect various tourist attractions to create a hot spring tourism route for maximum efficiency.
- Integrate cooperation from all sectors to drive towards the same goal which required integration of the collaboration. The development of the tourism is to promote tourism in order to create new tourism trends by presenting the way of life of the community, culture and local identity.
- Building a strong network which ready to develop and integrated tourism in the same direction and create sustainability.

References

- Chen, J. S., Prebensen, N., & Huan, T. C. (2008). Determining the Motivation of Wellness Travelers. *International Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 19(1), 103–115.
- Chulalongkorn University Intellectual Property Institute. (2017). Industry and technology trend analysis report: Tourism industry, good income and health tourism, Intellectual Property and innovation entrepreneur development project. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University Intellectual Property Institute. (In Thai)
- Department of Tourism. (2015). ASEAN Tourism Standards. Retrieved from <http://www.tourism.go.th/> (In Thai)
- Ministry of Tourism and Sports. (2015). Strategic of Thailand tourism B.E. 2015 - 2017. Retrieved from https://www.mots.go.th/ewt_dl_link.php?nid=7114. (In Thai)
- Scheyvens, R. (2002). *Tourism for Development: Empowering communities*. Harlow: Prentice Hall
- Smith, M. & Kelly, C. (2006). Wellness Tourism. *Tourism Recreation Research*, 31(1), 1–4.
- Teeranon, K. (2018). Thailand's wellness tourism: Situation and potential towards competition of ASEAN Region. *FEU Academic Review*, 2018 (12), 22-34. (In Thai)
- Global Wellness Institute.(2018). Global wellness tourism economy, November 2018. Retrieved from https://globalwellnessinstitute.org/wpcontent/uploads/2018/11/GWI_GlobalWellnessTourismEconomyReport.pdf
- Ufuk, A., Gulfer, B., Zehra, A., &Arzu, I. (2012). The International Patient's Portfolio and Marketing of Turkish Health Tourism. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 58, 1004-1007.
- WHO. (2000). *The world health report 2000 - health systems: improving performance*. Geneva, World Health Organization.
- Abraham, S, Brooke R. Noriega, Ju Young Shin (2018). College students eating habits and knowledge of nutritional requirements. *Journal of Nutrition and Human Health*, 2(1), 13-17.

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